

Challenges Teachers Face in Conducting Research: A Basis for Enhancement Training and Research Output

Analee T. Ongsansoy, Melfe Grace A. Sanchez, and Christie Anne D. Bihag
Palo I District
analee.ongsansoy@deped.gov.ph

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ABSTRACT

Conducting educational research has emerged as one of the most difficult tasks for the majority of teachers, particularly, since they have to put in more effort. This research looked into questions like these: a. What is educational research to the teachers? b. What are the challenges teachers face in conducting research? c. How do research help in the learning and development of the current issues? and d. What possible recommendation the participants can give as part of the solutions to the challenges they have encountered in conducting any research? The nature of the research being conducted is descriptive. Information was gathered from the teacher participants and underwent qualitative analysis. The study used one-

on-one face-to-face interview and focused group discussion. The study's findings showed that all of the participants have difficulties in conducting research which resulted to zero output in the district. It also highlighted the challenges teachers faced in conducting research, such as the absence of time, lack of in-depth knowledge, experience anxiety when writing and carrying out the research, and view research as a heavy work for them. Moreover, participants find it also difficult to choose an issue to be studied. One interesting finding is that almost every one of the participants have participated at least in any LAC sessions as a component of their education and growth that gave them the idea to develop their study. The researchers of this study have therefore created an action plan to somehow address the issue that teachers faced in conducting research.

Keywords: *Challenges; Educational Research; Descriptive Study; Qualitative*

INTRODUCTION

Research-driven advancements and improvements genuinely assist each person in preparing his or her knowledge with the required abilities. This is also true for the majority of educators who wish to recognize and address each issue in the field. But generating new information and using what is already known in an innovative way has been quite difficult for the majority of educators. Generally speaking, carrying out research is mainly carried out solely for requirements, promotion, and compliance.

In the current environment, many educators are urged to conduct study in order to pinpoint the issues and develop an answer. Action research, teacher research, school-based research, and classroom research have all been defined in teachers at the school and in the classroom carried out the current investigation. The main purpose of research is to investigate and pinpoint a problem or issue in the school and classroom which teacher-researchers hope to resolve by fully comprehending (Burns & Kurtoglu-Hooton, 2014).

Researching can truly help teachers advance their knowledge and abilities, despite the fact that it can be challenging to educators. Teachers view research as a crucial instrument for developing and presenting lessons to learners encouraging successful learning results. Additionally, it is useful and practical because it would greatly benefit the educators and the students as well. Additionally, Ulla, Barrera, and Acompañado (2017) believed that conducting research is crucial to teacher's development as professionals. They concurred that conducting research fosters critical self-reflection, which allows them to analyze and investigate issues in the classroom and school and their resolutions, and expands and improves their classroom teaching knowledge and abilities.

Additionally, Sarkar (2014) listed the following difficulties teachers face when conducting research: Obtaining consent to collect data comes first, followed by recruiting the target participants and any issues with using a research instrument. Nonetheless, teachers faced numerous challenges when doing their research, but this will guide us to a more effective method of finding fresh concepts and methods for the teaching and learning process. In light of this, the researchers looked into the obstacles and problems educators faced in carrying out research on education in Palo I District and the nation at large.

In the context of education, research has become a crucial component, successfully closing the gap between theory and practice. Its objective is to produce useful information that appeals to people in their daily lives, establishing a ripple impact that is advantageous to both people and their general community (Reason & Bradbury, 2013). This combination of action and research has received recognition on a global scale as a driving force behind inventiveness, providing a powerful remedy for the difficulties encountered in the field of education. DepEd, the Department of Education, in the Philippines has acknowledged the crucial role that research, as demonstrated by the guidelines of the DepEd Order No. 16 series 2017, which emphasize the value of research administration.

Literature Review

This study is strengthened by the latest literature on research protocols and teachers' real-challenging experiences in conducting research. Often, teachers are challenged in conducting research because of several reasons which hinder them to do so. With research, teachers realize that they can be a solution to many pressing problems in their respective schools.

The literature relative to the challenges of the teachers encountered in making researches clarifies the significant effort that it is really difficult on their part as well as the time constraints teachers face. Educators who manage to balance many obligations find it difficult to devote enough time and effort to carry out careful research projects (Tindowen and others, 2019).

Acknowledging and applauding the benefits of research on instructional strategies can encourage teachers even more to overcome obstacles and accept it as a useful instrument for ongoing pedagogical improvement. Furthermore, research is valued in the larger context of education as well as in personal fulfillment. When a particular research beneficial effects are recognized and honored, it fosters a collaborative learning culture in educational institutions in addition to inspiring individual teachers. Acknowledging educators' research efforts encourages information exchange and peer support, fostering a community of practice where creative concepts and strategies that work can thrive.

In addition to fostering strong professional ties amongst teachers, collaborative approach advances teaching approaches as a whole. Educational institutions can encourage a never-ending cycle of progress by creating an atmosphere that respects and values the results of research study, whereby teachers are motivated to work together to address problems and take advantage of research's revolutionary potential to raise the standard of education as a whole. The Revised Basic Education Curriculum (RBEC) is being replaced with the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum in the Philippines. Unprecedented professional obligations are placed on teachers (Ulla, 2018). A new era of educational challenges has been brought about by the forces of internationalization and globalization and in order to stay competitive, teachers must adopt creative teaching techniques and research-based procedures.

In light of this, the researcher aims to examine and comprehend how educators value conducting educational research and the particular challenges that educators at Palo I District encountered when conducting research throughout 2025–2026 academic year. The research's respondents will only be drawn from the whole district's educators. By looking at the particular challenges when acting, these educators come across research, the investigator seeks to clarify the elements affecting whether or not fulfillment of such studies within this educational establishment.

In enumerating different studies related to challenges in conducting research, it is necessary to clarify the challenges teachers face. Research has a significant impact on social and economic development. It is essential to expanding knowledge and creating a better society because it is a logical process that seeks to gain new perspectives and validate preexisting views and biases in order to improve society (Wagas et al., 2024; Islam, 2023; Janer et al., 2022). Islam & Samsudin (2020) further demonstrated that all forms of development began with doubting the existence of something, and as a result, research was created to help people advance and develop. Moreover, it is evident that teachers can also benefit from conducting research in the following ways (Byrne, 2018): a) they can help other teachers discover new and evidence-based teaching innovations and strategies; b) classroom research is easy to conduct and small-scale; c) it can be done in the classroom and at your convenience; and d) they can help psychologists and other experts discover new things.

Despite the benefits and advantages of conducting research, Anzaldo (2019) claims in their study that despite the advantages of professional development, teachers' workloads and supplementary responsibilities continue to be a barrier to conducting research. Teachers can occasionally feel frightened by conducting research because they believe it to be time-consuming and intricate. Ospanova (2016) asserts that conducting research aids in teachers' professional growth by fostering reflective thinking and boosting their self-assurance in their ability to find rapid solutions to issues. Given that educators have direct knowledge of the issues at hand, they are the ones who can provide answers within the four walls of the classroom. In addition to its effect on career advancement, numerous studies have demonstrated that conducting research enhances the quality of the teaching and learning process according to Ulla, (2017). All teachers are strongly supported by the Department of Education to develop school-based research. Although it is clear that educators in the Philippines face difficulties in conducting research, that's why there hasn't been much research produce.

In contrast, in other nations, they are committed to resolving these problems. According to Sarkar (2014) he discovered in Bangladesh that the difficulties in conducting research include gathering data, finding participants and issues with survey questionnaire use. Because of the teachers' limited time and that teachers were unable to complete their research due to workloads and the aforementioned difficulties. Although, educators struggle to comprehend their own research, lack of confidence in their organization, insufficient time and resources at the library, and absence of direction or understanding of research technique, and experience stress and annoyance on the procedure for conducting research.

Additionally, on the year 2016, the Basic Education Research Agenda (BERA) by the Department of Education saw the importance of adoption the basic research. It even encourages basic education research in the Philippines to be conducted and used in order to raise the department's level of service quality. Teachers, administrators, supervisors, and even non-teaching staff are urged to carry out research in order to address significant problems in the nation's educational system. (DepEd Order No. 39 s. 2016). Being included in the Individual Key Result Area (KRA) Researching became a component of the teacher assessment process, along with performance commitment and review. Sönmez and Akyel (2017) stress that practical experience obtained by performing research can lead to an expansion of research expertise investigation.

Similarly, working in groups or pairs, realistic learning techniques, and real-world research activities all helped students develop a positive outlook and a greater degree of research knowledge (Linden et al., 2012). Additionally, to be competent in research, one must possess technical writing abilities along

with the capacity to collect and evaluate data, operate independently, think critically, and use designing, sampling, and analysis. Research application in the real world and experience learning can both improve research competency (Davidson & Palermo, 2015). skills, participating in training, seminars, workshops, and research capacity-building programs (Toquero, 2021), conducting research-related tasks and activities (Khan et al., 2016), and dedicating oneself to a variety of research endeavors (Ivanenko et al., 2015).

Theoretical Framework

This study used a very applicable theory that specifically describes the challenges teachers encountered in conducting research. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is one of the most well-known theories in social psychology on the relationship between attitude and behavior. Fishbein's Attitude Theory Involving Multiple Attributes, which holds that behavioral impact is determined by behavioral attitude and that behavioral attitude is determined by expected behavioral results and their assessments, served as its inspiration. Fishbein and Ajzen then expanded the Theory of Multi attribute Attitude to develop the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which asserts that both behavioral attitude and subjective norm influence behavioral intention. However, because TRA assumes that action is entirely determined by personal desire, it has little ability to explain behavior that is not entirely driven by volitional control.

The theory of planned behavior (TPB), a social psychology theory was created by American professor Ayez based on the Theory of Rational Behavior (TRA). This important theoretical basis can be used to describe and forecast the behavior of reasonable people. According to this theory, "rational individuals" make specific behavioral decisions primarily due to three factors: behavioral attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

According to Rosela et al. (2019), behavioral attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control have a strong favorable influence on researchers' desire. Behavioral intention and perceived behavioral control have a major influence on research participation in school cooperation behavior (Ran, 2021). Therefore, the Theory of Planned Behavior predicts individual behavior as well as the factors that precede and impact it from the perspective of the psychological composition of rational people. Therefore, it is equally appropriate to look into how teachers engage in organized scientific research in a modern industrial setting. As a result, investigating how young instructors participate in structured scientific research at contemporary industrial set up is equally suitable.

Statement of the Problem

The study explores the challenges teachers experienced in conducting research studies. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is educational research?
2. What are the challenges teachers face in conducting research?
3. How do research help in the learning and development of the current issues?
4. What possible recommendation can you give as part of the solutions to the challenges that you have encountered in conducting any research?

Significance of the Study

The phenomenological study will be conducted to understand the challenges teachers encountered in conducting research and the possible recommendations teacher can give to enhance their knowledge about research. The result of this study will significantly benefit the following:

Department of Education (DepEd Officials). The result of the study will serve as an eye opener to the DepEd Officials on the challenges teachers face in conducting research. Moreover, this study would serve as basis for the department to formulate a DepEd Order or training that will surely help teachers embrace the beauty of research.

School Administrators. Task to enhance and update the Annual Improvement Plan for the specific training to be given to teachers as well as design an INSET training or LAC Session that is aligned to

research. This study will surely give insights as to what kind of support to be given to the teachers, like sending teachers to trainings Department Heads.

This study helps them guide the teachers in their respective departments to conduct a Learning Action Cell on the conduct of research which will enhance their knowledge and skills. Teachers. As the provider of basic education to our young learners, the result of this study will help them acquire the best knowledge and guidance on how to embrace the beauty of conducting research and encourage them to make and participate in the different research conference. Students.

This study will teach them the importance of conducting research and its opportunities if properly used with the guidance of their teachers. Researcher. This study's findings will provide future researchers with information on the challenges in conducting research.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study investigates the challenges teachers face in conducting research at Palo I District for school year 2025-2026. It looks into the common challenges that teachers face and possible recommendations that will answer the challenges encountered by teachers in conducting research. The participants are twelve teachers in Palo I District, Leyte Division.

The teachers are composed of ten elementary and two Junior High School only. The study focuses on the challenge's teachers face in conducting research in Palo I District. The researchers chose participants in Palo I District since no one of the twelve schools conducted research or submitted to the Leyte Division Office or publish any study in a referred journal. The none submission is a manifestation that most of them faced challenges in conducting research.

METHODS

Research Design

This study used a qualitative-phenomenology approach. Qualitative research offers viewpoints that allow for various study methods and situations (Yan et al., 2023). Grounded theory, ethnography, case studies, numerous case studies, and narratives can all contain it. This indicates that no statistical tools are required in order to analyze the results. In contrast, a phenomenology concentrates on people's actual experiences (Gagura, 2023). This implies that meaning ought to be deduced from on their conversation. Similarly, this methodology is specific in analyzing in-depth knowledge how these events gave people meaning (Stolz, 2023).

The content analysis was used to analyze the verbatim responses, particularly from the interview conducted, and confirmed responses from the focused group discussion to find themes and sub-themes. This study, therefore, used qualitative content analysis, which involves systematic analysis of the content, identifying and determining themes, words, or concepts in some texts (Hassan, 2024). Researchers use this analytical method to infer the meaning and relationships of themes, concepts, or a particular set of words (Columbia University, n.d.)

This study focused on the challenge's teachers face in conducting research in Palo I District Leyte Division. In this theory, there are some guiding principles following this constructivist thinking that we must remember when considering our role as educators. To answer the research questions presented in the previous chapter about the challenge's teachers face in conducting research, this study employed a phenomenological approach where it includes the researcher's point of view on the topic, information gathered from the research participants, and depiction of the experience from outside the context of the research itself. It will identify the challenges teachers face in conducting research. The perspective will allow the experiences of the research participants to be fully understood on a rich and in-depth level.

Phenomenology is an area of theory concerned primarily with participants' experiences. Its emphasis is on the world as lived by a person. Its focus is also on illuminating details and seemingly trivial aspects within the experience that may be taken for granted to create meaning and achieve a sense of understanding. It identifies and focuses to understand or comprehend the meanings of human experience as it is lived.

It provides a framework for a researcher to study lived experiences, marked as both a philosophy and methodological approach, in which the researcher engages with a few subjects to develop patterns and relationships of meaning (Cilesiz, 2009). In this phenomenological method, the questions encouraged the teacher participants to identify and share their challenges encountered in conducting research in the Palo I District Leyte Division and give their recommendations that will help encourage them to conduct or make researches out of the many issues arises during the School Monitoring Evaluation and Adjustment.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Palo I District, Leyte Division, which encountered challenges in conducting research.

Research Participants

In order to answer the research questions, the researchers chose participants in Palo I District. Twelve teachers under this district cooperated in a one-time interview. The researchers ask permission from the School Heads from where the teacher participants are under for a one-time interview and focused group discussion. This study used the phenomenological approach. Phenomenological approach was used to describe things that are already part of the world we live in. Events, circumstances, feelings, or ideas can all be considered phenomena (Patton, 2015). Phenomenology is both a philosophical movement and a collection of research methods that focus on understanding people's experiences. Simply put, phenomenology involves examining phenomena, which can be anything that a person consciously perceives or experienced. In essence, it's about getting a deeper insight into how people interpret the world around them.

Ethical Consideration

The study subscribed to the principles of informed consent, where all teacher participants are fully informed about the study's objective, and their safety is ensured. On the participants' rights, voluntary interview participation is essential. The researchers highly emphasize that the participants are free to withdraw from participating in the study at any stage if they wish to do so. Privacy ensures that the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants are always protected. Using offensive and discriminatory language is avoided in conducting the interview and the focus group discussion with all participants.

Lastly, trust that the participants are not subjected to any deception in this research process or its published outcomes and will have the right to know the conclusion of this study. Likewise, the researchers know and understand that using a person's previous work without proper acknowledgment should be strictly followed.

Data Gathering

The researchers seek approval from the office of the Superintendent of Leyte Division before conducting the study. The participants were asked to respond to the interview questionnaire to define (a) what is educational research, identify the (b) challenges teachers face in conducting research, know (c) how research help in the learning and development of the current issues, and give (d) possible recommendation that can be considered as solutions to the challenges they have encountered in conducting any research?

The researchers personally gathered the participants in one classroom for the one-time interview and FGD with the permission of the School Principal. Afterward, the researchers collected the twelve

teachers and informed them of the purpose of the interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). Each teacher participant was oriented with the purpose of the study and were requested to sign an Informed Consent Form before the start of the interview.

The researchers individually ask the prepared questions based on the interview guide questions. The responses of the teachers were recorded using cellphone. The other way of gathering the data is through an interview where the teachers can freely relate and share the challenges encountered in conducting research. Teachers are allowed to answer the questions collectively or individually. The interview lasts an hour only. Afterwards, a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) is conducted. During the data collection process, the responses of the teacher participants were recorded for interpretation with proper privacy protection.

Data Analysis

After the data collection, a record for each detailed interview was created, and critical conversation points were saved in a Word-format file. All the names and information of the participants were removed from all transcripts to ensure anonymity. The data sets were read many times to look for specific statements of meaning or quotes from the participants. Essential clusters of meaning were developed at the stage of the research process. And from that cluster of important statements, the researchers then wrote both textural and structural descriptions of how the participants encountered the challenges in conducting research. The textural description describes the real challenges of the participants in conducting research. In contrast, the structural description gives insights into the context that gave rise to the challenge's teachers experienced in conducting research (Creswell, 2013).

All the data were sorted into themes and sub-themes. The themes are the challenges that teacher participants experienced in conducting research. Sub-themes were the support that teacher participants can get and the possible recommendations teacher can give to surpass the challenges encountered in conducting research. Lastly, the textural and structural descriptions of the participants' usual challenges were presented.

Validation Techniques

One method, member checking, was employed in the study (Creswell, 2013). In order to confirm the veracity and accuracy of the data and conclusions, this member checking procedure examined data from research participants. In order to assess the validity of the findings, the researcher subsequently spoke with two educators who were left out of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the interviews and focused group discussions conducted with the teachers on the challenges that they have encountered in conducting research. The results will be presented in four parts. The first part presents the teachers definition of research. The second part is the challenges teachers encountered in conducting research. The third part is how the research help solve the learning and development of the current issues.

The last part shows the teacher's recommendations that can be considered as solution to the challenges that they have encountered in conducting research. The teacher's definition of research, challenges encountered in conducting research, the help of research in the learning and development and the possible recommendation that teachers can give on the challenges that they have encountered are presented based on the following themes.

Teacher's Definition of Research

Teacher participants defined research as a systematic and structured investigation that seeks to expand knowledge, uncover new insights, and provide evidence-based understanding in various fields. Others defined it as a systematic and disciplined inquiry that aims to discover, interpret, and expand knowledge in a specific field of study.

It is a process of investigation that goes beyond mere observation or gathering of information. Research involves formulating research questions or hypotheses, designing methodologies, collecting and analyzing data, and drawing meaningful conclusions. One participant said: “Educational research is the systematic, scientific study of education and learning processes with the goal of comprehending, enhancing, and assessing teaching, learning, and educational systems. It generates evidence that influences theory, practice, and policy using both quantitative and qualitative methodologies”. (T4, L5-L8)

Challenges Teachers Face in Conducting Research

Due to many school responsibilities, lots of school reports and lack of knowledge on how to access the available resources, teachers frequently face difficulties when undertaking research. Teachers find it challenging to balance their time between their teaching duties and academic research because of these obstacles. One participant mentioned that: “Due to severe workloads, lack of time and knowledge, inadequate training in research techniques, experience anxiety, restricted access to resources, and a lack of institutional support, teachers frequently face difficulties when undertaking research. Teachers find it challenging to strike a balance between their teaching duties and academic research because of these obstacles. Though there are some instances that the topic discussed during Learning Action Cell is research, still we lack the in-depth knowledge about it”. (T9, L12-L17)

Research Help in the Learning and Development

Research help because it offers evidence-based insights that inform teaching, learning, and policy creation, it is essential to solving contemporary concerns in education. It assists educators and institutions in overcoming presumptions and effectively addressing issues including curricular relevance, equity, mental health, and digital learning. One teacher participant added that: “It really helps a lot to us teachers, specifically, in our discussions because we were able to deliver an evidence-based lesson”. (T11, L24-L25)

Possible Recommendation

These are some suggestions that teacher participants mentioned to address the difficulties they face when conducting research. These recommendations center on doable, institutional, and individual tactics that can help educators make research more feasible and long-lasting. One participant highlighted that: “DepEd through the different Regional or Division Offices should conduct training workshop to all teachers nationwide, not to the selected few only. This is I think is one way of supporting the teachers. Another is every District should come up with District Research Congress or School Head must include this in the AIP budget and come up with an In-Service training” (T1, L30-L33).

CONCLUSION

The study reveal that teachers really encountered challenges in conducting research because of the following serious reasons like severe workloads, lack of time and knowledge, inadequate training in research techniques, experience anxiety, lack of knowledge on the access to resources, and a lack of institutional support, teachers frequently face difficulties when undertaking research. Teachers find it also challenging to strike a balance between their teaching duties and academic research because of these obstacles, though, there are some instances that the topic was discussed during Learning Action Cell (LAC).

On the part of how research help the teachers on their lessons, the participants emphasized that it really helps them, specifically, in their discussions because they were able to deliver an evidence-based lessons. Ultimately, findings from this study present a hopeful perspective that DepEd will give equal opportunities to all teachers to attend training workshops aligned or related to research and gain in depth knowledge that will help them improve their teaching strategies that is evidence-based and scientifically anchored.

Summary

This study investigated the challenges teachers face in conducting research. The researchers aimed to identify the challenges in conducting research, how do it help in the learning development and the possible recommendations that teachers can give to address the difficulties that they have encountered. This study employed a qualitative research method, specifically the phenomenology approach, so as to explore the challenges faced by the teachers in conducting research.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions arrived at, it is recommended that DepEd through the Regional and Division Offices must conduct training workshops about research that will improve teacher's performance and will somehow address school issues in conducting research. Another is every District must conduct a District Research Congress or School Head must include this in the AIP budget so that it will be given an allocation during the In-Service training, if the Regional or Division Offices will not able to conduct a research training. District and Schools must also make an Action Plan for the immediate realization of the said training.

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